

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

D8.1. Practice abstracts - batch 2

Date of delivery: **31/07/2025**

Authors: **Seng Kiong Kok, Duc Trinh Tran, Therese Marie Uppstrøm Pankratov, Pamela Steele, Hellen Wanza, Sarah Joseph, Syed Yasir Ahmad, Waqar Ahmad, Yumiko Soulier, Nguyen Vinh Hoa, Virva Tuomala, Anaïs Loudières.**

Institutions: **RMIT, Vietnam; Innovasjon Norge, Norway; PSA, Kenya; KLU, Germany; IMC Croatia, Croatia; Solvoz, Netherlands; VNRC, Vietnam; Hanken, Finland; Euronovia, France.**

**Funded by the
European Union**

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DOCUMENT TRACK INFORMATION

PROJECT INFORMATION	
Project acronym	WORM
Project title	Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation
Starting date	01/01/2024
Duration	24 months
Call identifier	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CIRCBIO-01
Grant Agreement No	101135392

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION	
Deliverable number	D8.1
Work Package number	WP8
Deliverable title	Practice abstracts - batch 2
Authors	Seng Kiong Kok (RMIT), Duc Trinh Tran (RMIT), Therese Marie Uppstrøm Pankratov (IN), Pamela Steele (PSA), Hellen Wanza (PSA), Joseph Sarah (KLU), Syed Yasir Ahmad (IMC), Waqar Ahmad (IMC), Yumiko Soulier (Solvoz), Nguyen Vinh Hoa (VNRC), Virva Tuomala (Hanken), Anaïs Loudières (Euronovia)
Due date	31/08/2025
Submission date	31/07/2025
Type of deliverable	R
Dissemination level	PU

REVISION TABLE

VERSION	CONTRIBUTORS	DATE	DESCRIPTION
V0.1	Anaïs Loudières (Euronovia)	13/06/2025	First draft
V0.2	Seng Kiong Kok (RMIT), Duc Trinh Tran (RMIT), Pamela Steele (PSA), Hellen Wanza (PSA), Yumiko Soulier (Solvoz)	15/07/2025	Updated draft after contribution
V0.3	Therese Marie Uppstrøm Pankratov (IN), Joseph Sarah (KLU), Syed Yasir Ahmad (IMC), Waqar Ahmad (IMC), Nguyen Vinh Hoa (VNRC)	17/07/2025	Updated draft after contribution
V0.4	Virva Tuomala (Hanken)	29/07/2025	Updated draft after contribution
V1	Anaïs Loudières (Euronovia)	30/07/2025	Final version for submission

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BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM

WORM aims to design guidelines and support actions for circular economy in the humanitarian sector. It integrates bio-based technological solutions, leverages procurement for waste reduction, improves waste management methods and prioritises the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component. Following a collaborative and multi-actor approach, WORM brings together medical and humanitarian organisations, procurement service providers, logistics providers, waste management services and academic partners.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392.

The aim of this document is to share the resulting innovative knowledge from WORM on the [EIP-AGRI \(the AGRICultural European Innovation Partnership\) website](#) for wide dissemination to practitioners and end-users.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

The [EIP-AGRI project database](#) showcases innovative projects from across Europe that promote innovation and knowledge exchange for agriculture, forestry and rural areas. A special effort is made to share knowledge and solutions that are ready to be put into practice. To this end, WORM publishes its innovative results in the form of summaries for practitioners in the common EIP-AGRI format to facilitate the uptake of the project. Eight practice abstracts were identified by the partners for this second batch and submitted to the EIP-AGRI project database. This brings the total number of practices identified by WORM to twelve.

ANNEX 1: EIP-AGRI database extract

PROJECT - RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation

PROJECT IDENTIFIER: 2024HE_101135392_WORM

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Context

Climate change is a main driver for humanitarian need. Yet, humanitarian operations contribute to environmental pollution and degradation; disaster relief rarely leaving time to consider long-term consequences, and international humanitarian organisations face frequent criticism for their lack of environmental policies despite their do-no-harm mandate. Waste management is an integral part of the environmental sustainability of a humanitarian operation.

Waste management is a complex area as it involves not only a myriad of organisations and sectors within international humanitarian organisations, but also private sector actors and contextual infrastructure. International humanitarian organisations further burden waste management in disaster relief areas, and issues with waste management were identified in almost all phases of the humanitarian operation.

Responding to these challenges, in 2022, DG ECHO introduced its new humanitarian logistics policy, which aims to make the delivery of humanitarian aid more efficient, effective, and green.

WORM contributes to tackling these challenges in two distinct settings: field hospital deployments, and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component.

Objectives

WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments, and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component.

Across these settings, the project focuses on several cross-cutting focus areas:

- To identify and integrate bio-based solutions in the humanitarian context for waste treatment;
- To use the full potential of sustainable procurement as a gatekeeper for waste avoidance and gateway for innovative solutions implementation;
- To propose safer and more environmentally responsible waste treatment methods;
- To enhance local awareness of improved waste management through targeted and community-based campaigns;
- To provide guidelines and policy recommendations for reducing the environmental impact and maximizing the socio-economic effects of humanitarian operations

Activities

The WORM project is structured over 3 phases:

- Phase 1 - Prioritisation (M1-M6)

Scoping exercise of commonly used product groups that could qualify for seeking bio-based alternative solutions, a waste stream analysis of field hospital settings, and collecting procurement practices.

- Phase 2 - Evaluation of alternatives (M7-M12)

Sustainability assessment of bio-based solutions to be integrated into procurement processes, analysis of local innovations in waste management and policy recommendations for their scaling up.

- Phase 3 - Policy & implementation (M13-M24)

Implementation of alternatives through the development of standard operational procedures (SOPs) for the use, reuse and transfer options of field hospitals. Examination of waste management from a socio-economic perspective (livelihoods, safety and hygiene of waste pickers). Assessment of the limits and consequences of introducing bio-based solutions in the humanitarian context.

Other comments

WORM seeks to identify bio-based technologically innovative solutions for the humanitarian context, **focusing on pre-selected high priority items** which are needed in field hospital deployments. The product groups selected for WORM are:

- Personal protective equipment (PPE)
- Syringes and needles
- Sharps and containers
- Plastic body bags
- Temporary water/sludge bladders

These product groups are the central element of WORM.

Project details

Main funding source

Horizon Europe (EU Research and Innovation Programme)

Type of Horizon project

Multi-actor project

Project acronym

WORM

[CORDIS Fact sheet](#)

Project contribution to CAP specific objectives

- SO4. Agriculture and climate mitigation
- Environmental care
- Preserving landscapes and biodiversity
- Fostering knowledge and innovation

Project contribution to EU Strategies

Achieving climate neutrality

EUR 1 499 664.60

Total budget

Total contributions including EU funding.

EUR 1 499 664.60

EU contribution

Any type of EU funding.

Project keyword(s)

Circular economy, incl. waste, by-products and residues >

Supply chain, marketing and consumption >

Resources

Links

[🔗 WORM Bio-based solutions Catalogue](#)

12 Practice Abstracts

1. A plug and play waste management model for humanitarian organisations in diverse settings: A decision-support tool for deployments

A key solution to achieving the objectives of the WORM project is with **a plug and play model that is developed as a decision support tool for deploying humanitarian organizations across various settings**. This decision support tool is developed to provide humanitarian organizations **with information on local processes, requirements, settings, policies, and regulations so as to guide their procurement and waste management practices**.

With the myriad of medical supplies and products that are used over a humanitarian deployment, the plug and play model will highlight dependency linkages across different operational and strategic parameters, for example, duration and type of deployment, and operational role. The model will also enable humanitarian organization to rank operation and strategic objectives and will consider such dynamics when providing guidance, for example, is economic efficiency prioritized over capacity to adopt sustainable practices for waste management. Based upon such input parameters, the model will then highlight the local humanitarian waste management ecosystem offering insight into the available waste treatment methods and technologies, list of local waste management service providers, and list of local regulatory requirements. For now, the plug and play will be built for Vietnam and Kenya but will be extended to more settings going forward.

The implications of the plug and play model for humanitarian organizations are that they will **get a rapid assessment of the underlying landscape of waste management within their operational settings**. This rapid assessment tool will be utilized **to understand mismatches between organizational capacity and the local waste management infrastructure of the country of operations**, and the specificities of local regulations that require engagement.

2. Greening humanitarian response through innovation friendly procurement

The **innovation friendly procurement approach is a tool that can help humanitarian actors balance the need to safeguard against corruption and tight budgets, while maximising the impact of the procurement, and manage sustainability considerations**. The process lends itself particularly well for a strategically important procurement connected to an organisation's core business, where there is little competition in the market and a buyer wants to stimulate market growth, and in areas or markets that evolve quickly. The **differences between an ordinary procurement and an innovation friendly procurement** lies in:

1. The approach to the needs assessment, with an increased focus on the outcome that is sought with the procurement and less on the input.
2. The introduction of an open and transparent dialogue between the buyer and the private sector, an element that is often prevented by humanitarian organisations' procurement regulations today.
3. In the formulation of the specifications in the request for proposals. These should be formulated around the performance and impact sought, not on technical specifications describing a solution.

The **added value of adopting the innovation friendly procurement approach:**

- A more inclusive procurement process fostering improved dialogue between the supplier and the purchaser and ensuring that the product or service delivered from the suppliers meet the needs of the beneficiaries.
- De-risking the procurement process by contracting a product or service based on performance-based specifications.
- Potential for increased impact and value creation for the target group building on a thorough and user-centric needs assessment.

Additional information

Recommendations:

- Define the needs and not the means: **developing performance-based (or open) specifications that responds to the humanitarian need** identified will allow suppliers to be innovative and increase the chances of finding new and better ways to meet the needs.
- Ensure buy-in from management: **Sustainable procurement should be a strategic decision**. Promote an inclusive process and involve relevant stakeholders in the process of designing procurement specifications.
- **Build competence:** Adopting an innovation friendly procurement approach might require new competence and training of staff in humanitarian organisations and other relevant stakeholders.
- **Involve the market:** Bring the outcome of the needs assessment to the market to educate potential suppliers about actual needs and contexts, and to educate humanitarian experts about what type of solutions are available that can meet the needs.

3. Scoping exercise

WORM seeks to establish common policies and standard operating procedures (SOP) for the humanitarian context and particularly any environmental repercussions incurred during operations involving field hospital deployments. **With LCAs of prioritised product groups conducted, it is possible to identify and prioritize improvement opportunities, and/or compare different products or processes. These comparisons are made between fossil-fuel based products and bio-based or -sourced products.** The LCA is also used to determine the environmental impact of current waste management strategies for hazardous medical waste. This will also help to determine alternatives to e.g. incineration, which can cause harmful emissions and air pollution, and is one of the common ways of disposing of waste in many contexts. Alternatives include sanitary landfills, pressure steam or microwave sterilisation, and chemical disinfection. **The trade-offs between alternatives are highlighted with causal loop**

diagrams (CLD). CLDs provide comprehensive information on the effects of decisions by conceptualising the balancing or reinforcing effects of factors. Trade-offs include:

- environmental friendliness of bio-sourced products versus their durability
- material selection and hygiene requirements
- increase in bio-based material versus food security, deforestation and climate change
- change in materials vs the livelihoods of waste pickers

Dialogue between stakeholders in the humanitarian supply chain is crucial for environmental sustainability. Neutral guidelines and policies would enable IHOs to implement environmental guidelines on strategic level. The emphasis has thus far been on transactional processes such as procurement, whereby the holistic view of the organizational strategy remains neglected. **An output of WORM will be a catalogue of products used in humanitarian contexts, where crucial details of these products will be clearly available for end users.**

4. Sustainability in humanitarian procurement

The workshop produced several significant outcomes:

1. **Framework Development:** Participants collaboratively contributed to the draft sustainability framework that prioritizes key criteria across three dimensions: environmental, social, and economic. This framework serves as a guideline for integrating sustainability into humanitarian procurement practices.
2. **Increased Engagement:** Feedback was gathered through polls and breakout sessions, emphasizing a collective commitment to advancing sustainability in humanitarian operations.
3. **Consensus on Criteria:** A consensus emerged on the necessity of mandatory environmental requirements and the importance of establishing standardized supplier assessments to ensure systematic integration of sustainability in procurement policies.

End-users, including humanitarian organizations and procurement officers, can implement the results of this project **by utilizing the developed sustainability framework in their procurement strategies. By adopting the standardized criteria outlined in the framework, organizations can enhance procurement processes, reduce environmental impact, and improve supplier engagement.** Additionally, there is a critical need for a go-to knowledge base that provides all stakeholders with access to relevant information and resources. This knowledge base has materialized in the WORM project into a new key deliverable of the WORM project—the **bio-based catalogue of product categories—designed to showcase sustainable options available in the market for humanitarians and health workers globally (to be launched Q4 2024)**. The main added value for end-users lies in the opportunity to align their procurement practices with sustainability objectives, thereby contributing to more responsible and effective humanitarian operations. The framework not only provides a practical tool for integrating

sustainability into procurement but also promotes collaboration among stakeholders, enabling a unified approach.

5. Making circular economy business models work in humanitarian contexts

A key reason why efforts to introduce new waste management solutions in humanitarian response fail is a limited focus on the systems innovation that is needed to support the implementation and scale of a new solution. Implementing circular waste management models requires systems-thinking; this includes considering whole supply chains, local markets, user behavior, demand, and financing. What might seem like an incremental change often has ripple effects in fragile settings that require a more systematic approach to succeed. To develop and ensure sustainable circular economy business models it is important to consider how different elements of waste handling interact and are interrelated to create new value flows. To make the implementation of one innovative solution work might require the introduction of complementary innovations e.g. the introduction of repair services in a refugee camp will be strengthened by the procurement of more repairable technology, improved training programmes, implementation of a waste currency that support waste collection etc. When evaluating the potential of new waste management solutions consider these three questions: Is the waste management system complete from solution bought to waste handled? Are all relevant actors incentivized to do their part? Will all relevant actors consider the new system better than the alternative? If the answer to any of these questions is no, the system is likely to fail. To realize a circular economy at scale in the humanitarian sector, it is important to

- Focus on agile ways to finance up-front costs.
- Identify high impact interventions that actively include people affected by crises. Initiatives will fail if the user perspective is not represented. Interventions that are environmentally beneficial could have unintended consequences for efficient aid delivery.
- Set up supporting procedures and frameworks, e.g. innovation friendly procurement processes that support the uptake of innovative solutions.

6. A technical and economic assessment of bio-based alternatives for priority medical supplies for humanitarian use

Globally, the market for bio-based medical products is expanding rapidly, driven in part by evolving environmental regulations, material innovation for biodegradables, and, more importantly for WORM, increased healthcare demand.

WORM conducted a bio-based alternative assessment of five identified priority products for use within field hospitals during humanitarian deployments, namely, PPE, syringes and needles, sharps containers, body bags, and temporary water or sludge bladders.

The adoption of such bio-based alternatives is still plagued by many issues, including scalability of technology and supply chain limitations whilst contending with challenging humanitarian settings where there can be technological and knowledge gaps. Moreover, whilst costs are falling with continual developments in technology and innovative business models, cost-effectiveness remains an obstacle as institutions contend with balancing performance and affordability. Across our focal countries of Vietnam and Kenya, we observe limited local availability of bio-based alternatives, along with unclear technical specifications in relation to international medical standards.

Some of the key findings from this exercise are:

- › That there is substantial bio-based material development across all five priority products.
- › Uptake of bio-based alternatives by humanitarian entities is still limited.
- › Availability of bio-based alternatives in local market settings is limited but technologies are present for processing of base materials.

Practical implications include:

- › Classification of key bio-based material development across the five priority products enabling practitioners insight into alternatives.
- › Local market evaluation of bio-based alternatives including technical specifications to discern adherence to required standards for humanitarian deployments.
- › Identification of key local market participant to further contact and procurement practices for local and international humanitarian agencies.

Additional information

From a demand-side, there will be a need to better understand the procurement practices of humanitarian agencies in motivating the shift to and uptake of bio-based alternatives within humanitarian activities so as to furnish stakeholders with further insight into such decision making.

A subsequent supply-side examination of drive from local and regional manufacturers and distributors to further our understanding of the landscape of bio-based materials is important so as to bridge procurement and distribution channels.

7. Non-burn disinfection alternatives to improve medical waste management in humanitarian settings

Medical waste mismanagement in humanitarian and emergency field settings poses a threat to public health, the safety of waste handlers, and environmental sustainability. Effective medical waste management is essential in these settings, yet many still rely on incineration, a method that is energy-intensive and produces harmful emissions. The disinfection SWOT analysis, conducted by Pamela Steele Associates (PSA) under the EU-funded WORM project, evaluated non-destructive disinfection methods suitable for humanitarian operations. The study explored practical alternatives such as microwaving, autoclaving and chemical disinfection, to replace or complement incineration, based on field interviews, a literature review, and site visits in Kenya. Key informants validated the findings during a validation workshop.

The findings revealed that while autoclaves and microwaves offer safer, low-emission solutions, their adoption is hindered by high maintenance costs and a lack of technical know-how. For example, microwaving ensures high-level internal disinfection at medium temperatures, while autoclaving is a reliable method over time. Chemical disinfection is widely used for the pre-treatment of infectious liquid waste; however, it requires trained personnel and safe handling procedures. Many healthcare facilities still rely on outdated incinerators or unsafe open burning, especially in resource-constrained areas.

In humanitarian operations, adopting autoclave or microwave systems could significantly reduce emissions, occupational hazards, and post-crisis environmental burdens. Practitioners should prioritize

waste segregation at the source, invest in local training, and pair low-emission technologies with behavioural change.

While initial investments are high, implementing these solutions improves compliance and minimizes health and environmental risks. The benefits outweigh the costs when factored into long-term resilience, especially in fragile healthcare ecosystems.

Additional information

Implementing sustainable disinfection technologies requires financial investment, infrastructure, and skilled personnel. Scaling adoption requires coordinated national policy support, public-private partnerships, integrating medical waste management into emergency preparedness plans and investment in fit-for-context innovation. Current barriers include high costs of autoclaves and microwaves, insufficient awareness, and weak enforcement of segregation protocols.

Recommendations include deploying mobile treatment units tailored for field hospitals; strengthening training for waste handlers and WASH teams; mainstreaming biodegradable PPE and supply procurement; and advocating for emission control filters where incineration is unavoidable.

Sustained monitoring, capacity building, and community involvement are essential for achieving long-term impact and scalability across humanitarian contexts. Investing in sustainable disinfection enhances public health, reduces long-term costs, and fosters climate-resilient humanitarian responses.

8. Stakeholder engagement workshop and webinar on Waste management practices

The WORM project tackled waste management gaps in humanitarian hospitals and Emergency Medical Teams (EMTs) via a lifecycle approach. It included source segregation, reusable and repairable items, local maintenance, and reverse logistics, along with improved donation planning. Innovations like involving local recyclers, gasification instead of open burning, and modular procurement were highlighted. The web events addressed waste management challenges in field hospitals, particularly where infrastructure is limited and regulations are weak. They promoted sustainable, integrated systems aligned with humanitarian workflows across deployment phases.

The project developed waste management guidelines tailored to field conditions, emphasizing factors like budget, local training, and compliance, and suggested decentralized, collaborative solutions. The workshop demonstrated tools such as preventive maintenance, repair partnerships, and waste committees. The webinar highlighted successful practices from Japan and Sweden, as well as field-driven alternatives to incineration.

Practitioners should integrate waste management into operations early, train staff on segregation, and build local partnerships for waste handling and repair. Investing in training and procurement upfront can lower long-term costs and reduce environmental harm. Benefits include improved hygiene, reduced injury risk, lower environmental impact, and more efficient logistics.

WORM organized a global webinar/workshop with key EMTs and field hospital actors. Participants shared best practices, challenges, and recommendations on various waste management areas, including usage, reuse, maintenance, repair, recycling, refurbishment, reverse logistics, and handover. These are compiled into a summary of field learnings, now being reviewed against existing SOPs from

various organizations. This review will help develop practical, context-appropriate, and harmonized SOPs, which are currently in the draft stage.

9. Life Cycle Assessment of bio-based medical items and cleaner waste solutions for field hospitals

The WORM project addresses the environmental impact of humanitarian operations by evaluating both the materials used in essential items and their subsequent waste treatment. Using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), the project compared conventional materials—such as polypropylene (PP), polyester, polyethylene (PE), and synthetic rubber—with bio-based alternatives like polylactic acid (PLA from maize), bio-polyisoprene (natural rubber), cotton, and cardboard. These materials were analysed across eight priority products, including facemasks, gloves, gowns, and sharps containers.

The findings show that bio-based materials can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and fossil resource use during production. However, they may increase impacts, such as freshwater ecotoxicity, due to agricultural inputs. At the end-of-life stage, bio-based products generally perform better, especially when open burning is avoided. Among waste treatment options, autoclaving consistently showed the lowest environmental impact, making it a promising alternative to incineration in field hospitals.

Practitioners can reduce environmental harm by:

1. Prioritizing bio-based materials for items like facemasks, gloves, and sharps containers, especially when biodegradable options are available;
2. Avoiding open burning and exploring less-destructive waste treatments such as autoclaving or microwaving, which are safer and cleaner;
3. Considering renewable energy sources to power waste treatment equipment, further lowering emissions;
4. Engaging suppliers early to identify bio-based alternatives and ensure compatibility with local waste infrastructure.

While some alternatives may involve higher upfront costs or require new equipment, the long-term benefits include reduced pollution, improved health outcomes, and alignment with sustainability goals—making operations more resilient and responsible.

10. Community engagement in humanitarian waste management: Lessons from Vietnam's WORM Project

In Thai Nguyen province, Vietnam, the Vietnam Red Cross Society (VNRC) demonstrated how local communities can become central drivers of sustainable waste management. Instead of viewing waste solely as a technical or municipal issue, VNRC involved students, teachers, and informal waste workers in meaningful, low-cost environmental actions. The March 2025 campaign, '*Raising Community Awareness on Waste Management*', engaged over 900 participants in activities such as music performance, schoolyard cleanups, environmental art projects, and the introduction of tri-bin sorting systems in two schools. Students also planted 32 trees and created over 200 recycling-themed projects. Knowledge assessments revealed that 80% of students improved their understanding and behaviors related to waste separation. The campaign extended its reach through 4000 flyers and 12 media stories.

This inclusive, community-centered model is built on volunteerism, youth engagement, and strong local networks. It requires minimal financial investment but generates significant benefits: enhanced environmental awareness, community ownership, and recognition for informal workers. To scale this impact, VNRC will organize a follow-up event in Khanh Hoa Province on July 29, 2025, titled '*Together with Waste Collectors – Connecting Communities, Protecting the Environment*'. This upcoming campaign will unite 300 participants—waste collectors, volunteers, and residents—in mangrove planting (1 hectare), open dialogues, and a public commitment to '*Live Green – Live Clean*'.

Facilitators of success include local government support, social media outreach, and youth-led initiatives. Challenges include limited funding and lack of formal recognition for waste workers. Future steps involve developing school toolkits, supporting circular economy education, and integrating waste collectors into local planning. The key message: when communities co-create waste solutions, they build ownership, inclusion, and lasting change.

11. Community-driven campaigns to raise awareness on medical waste management in Kisumu, Kenya

In Kenya, the mismanagement of medical waste, especially incinerated mixed waste, poses health and environmental hazards. Through the EU-funded WORM project, informed by the findings from the field study on the SWOT of disinfection methods, Pamela Steele Associates (PSA) implemented a targeted local awareness campaign in Kisumu to address this issue. The campaign focused on engaging community stakeholders, including healthcare workers and health and environmental policymakers, to raise awareness about the dangers of poor waste management, with a focus on incineration, and encourage the adoption of safer, sustainable alternatives using locally tailored approaches.

A range of behaviour change outreach materials was developed, including brochures, pamphlets, and posters, that outlined the risks of toxic emissions from incineration and provided sustainable alternatives. These materials were distributed across the county by trained unemployed youth. Three murals were also painted in 3 local healthcare facilities, illustrating key messages in a community-friendly format.

Creative performances, including poems and drama, delivered by the Misango Arts Ensemble, were showcased during a preview on May 31st and at the main World Environment Day event on June 5th, held in Kisumu. These performances targeted community members, students, healthcare professionals, and environmental regulators, such as the National Environment Management Authority (NEMA), to amplify their impact and encourage action.

The campaign activities raised awareness among over 2,000 individuals, including public health officers, community members and empowered youth through active participation in mural painting and outreach activities.

This model can be replicated in other counties or humanitarian contexts by developing culturally relevant Information, Education, and Communication materials and working with local youth groups and creatives. It drives meaningful discussion on alternatives to incineration.

Additional information

The campaign was part of Task 8.3 under the WORM project, focusing on localized citizen engagement through creative and informative methods. Community members, especially youth, played a central role in its implementation, providing a dual impact: raising awareness and building local capacity.

Unemployed youth volunteers distributed printed materials and participated in mural creation at Lumumba Hospital, Jaramogi Oginga Odinga Teaching & Referral Hospital (JOOTRH), and Kisumu County Referral Hospital (KCRH).

The creative arts component, delivered by PSA's partner, the Misango Arts Ensemble, proved highly effective in reaching diverse audiences. The performances focused on improper disposal of hazardous medical waste and the risks it poses, while offering alternative practices aligned with circular economy principles. The poem and drama sessions were not only informative but also fostered emotional engagement, creating a sense of ownership among attendees.

PSA collaborated closely with healthcare workers and policy stakeholders to ensure the messages were contextually accurate and practically relevant. The team also participated in the VSO Network's pre-World Environment Day forum, positioning the campaign within broader environmental sustainability conversations in Kisumu County.

The next phase of the campaign includes a stakeholder workshop aligned with the WORM General Assembly, where experts will share policy insights and community actors will present their perspectives. This continuation will provide an opportunity for deeper dialogue and collaborative strategy development on sustainable waste management in humanitarian and public health settings.

This approach demonstrates the potential of integrating creative arts, youth engagement, and scientific messaging to drive behaviour change and institutional reflection on harmful practices like incineration.

Supply market intelligence with the bio-based solutions catalogue

The Supply Market Intelligence (SMI) study explores the bio-based alternatives of WORM prioritised product groups: syringes and needles, personal protective equipment, sharps containers, body bags, and temporary sludge bladders.

The objective of the SMI is to establish which bio-sourced and biodegradable alternatives already exist for these product groups, how ready they are for direct use in the humanitarian context, and how they would need to be developed further for the humanitarian industry to adopt them into use. A significant step is establishing what kind of information is needed by the practitioners to adopt bio-based solutions into their processes, as well as interpret and disseminate the information.

There are significant economic and technical barriers in the healthcare industry that require solutions to ensure the actual contribution to sustainability goals, and the stringent product standards within the healthcare industry

The conditions under which humanitarian markets, and therefore also field hospitals, operate are characterised by volatility, supply chain disruptions, limited, dilapidated or destroyed infrastructure, and increased vulnerabilities. In field hospitals, balancing environmental sustainability with practicality is a constant challenge. The costs of adopting bio-based or biodegradable materials often include hidden

factors, such as rising extraction and production costs, transportation, and compliance with medical device regulations.

To enhance availability and access to bio-based and bio-degradable products, WORM has launched a catalogue of products which fulfil environmental sustainability criteria (https://worm.solvoz.com/en_GB). This portal is fully open access and available in several crucial languages (English, French, Ukrainian among others). The catalogue caters to manufacturers, who can showcase their products; experts and researchers; and finally NGOs and other organisations, who can establish their specific needs.

Contacts

Project email

✉ contact@wormproject.eu

Project coordinator

SVENSKA HANDELSHOGSKOLAN (HANKEN)

Project coordinator

✉ humlog@hanken.fi 🌐 [Website](#) ↗ ☰ Research institute

Project partners

Solvoz

Project partner

🌐 [Website](#) ↗ ☰ Processor or retailer

Finnish Red Cross

Project partner

🌐 [Website](#) ↗ ☰ NGO

RMIT University Vietnam

Project partner

🌐 [Website](#) ↗ ☰ Research institute

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